

Table: Data Extraction Form

Title:	DOI:	
Name of article:	Country of publication:	Year of issue:
Conference or journal:		
Authors:		
Abstract:		
Type of research (classification by [17]): Validation research <input type="checkbox"/> Evaluation research <input type="checkbox"/> Proposed solution <input type="checkbox"/> Philosophical article <input type="checkbox"/> Opinion article <input type="checkbox"/> Article on personal experience <input type="checkbox"/>		
Type of solutions presented: Conceptual definition <input type="checkbox"/> Causes, effects, impacts and limitations <input type="checkbox"/> Evaluation methods or techniques <input type="checkbox"/> Technological tools <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial validation <input type="checkbox"/> Documentation methodologies <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>		
Breve descripción de la propuesta:		
Results:		
Limitations of the proposal:		
Research alternatives:		